

PROMOTING EMPLOYMENT BY THE DEVELOPMENT OF FAMILY ENTREPRENEURSHIP

Iskandarov Sunnatillo Bahridin o'g'l

assistant of the department of real economy of the
Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service

Annotatsiya: Maqolada oilaviy tadbirkorlikning vujudga kelishi va rivojlanishi, oilaviy biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikning ijtimoiy samaradorligini ta'minlashda manfaatlar ustuvorligi masalasi tahlil etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: tadbirkorlik, savdogarlik, ishbilarmonlik, hunarmandchilik, xususiy mulk, mulkdor, kichik biznes, farovonlik, halollik, to'g'ri so'zlilik, oilaviy tadbirkorlik, inson tabiati, xalq farovonligi, ijtimoiy – ma'naviy taraqqiyot, tijoratchilar, mulkdorlar, kasb-hunar axloqi, bozor iqtisodiyoti, rejali taqsimot, kasanachilik, ijtimoiy – iqtisodiy taraqqiyot.

Аннотация: В статье, рассматриваются вопросы предпринимательстве, сделано попытка кратко показать историю возникновения и сущность семейного бизнеса и предпринимательства.

Ключевие слова: предпринимательство, занятие ремеслом, частная собственность, собственник, малый бизнес, честность, правдивость, семейное предпринимательство, природа человека, благосостояние народа, социально – духовное развитие, коммерсанты, класс собственников, профессиональная этика, рыночная экономика, плановое распределение, народные промыслы, социально – экономическое развитие.

Abstract: This article is devoted to the arising and developing of business undertakings, analysis the social efficiency of providing benefits of steadfast matters the family business and free enterprise.

Keywords: businessman, merchant, skills, usury, occupation craft, private

property, owner, small business, key of well-being, profpity, truthful, family business is a key to peoples prosperity, family enter premiership, human nature, peoples, economical – enlightmat development comers man, property owners class, professional ethics marketing, economy planned destitution, handcraft, socio – economical development.

In the early stages of economic formation, the idea of entrepreneurship came into existence in order to monitor the daily economic activity. Early entrepreneurs were merchants. From this point of view, it will be known that entrepreneurship existed on the territory of Uzbekistan many centuries before BC. The strong development of entrepreneurial Commerce in our country dates back to the early centuries, when the Great Silk Road was formed.

From the moment our country gained independence to the present day, it is the attention to small business, and in recent years to family entrepreneurship, that has been carried out in order to ensure a calm, serene and comfortable stay for each family. The development of the country is considered to be inextricably linked with the peace, prosperity, employment of families. This attention was paid to the level of the law, and in 2012 the law “on the dam of family entrepreneurship“ was adopted. The main purpose of this law is to create the necessary legislative framework for the development of family entrepreneurship as an important form of small business and private entrepreneurship in various sectors of the economy, to provide legal guarantees for family business and to create new employment opportunities. The adoption of the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan” on family entrepreneurship " will be an important factor in the further development and development of small business and private entrepreneurship in our country, first of all in the neighborhoods, its share in the gross domestic product. It is in this law that the opportunities, privileges, rights and obligations of Olivier entrepreneurs, their protection by the state and its guarantees are widely covered. It is precisely in Chapter 6 of this law that “guarantees of freedom of activity of the Family Enterprise” are indicated. In

addition to the above listed examples, it is possible to cite the following:

- State support of the family enterprise;
- Nationalization, confiscation and requisition of property of Family Enterprise;
- Freedom of the activity of the family enterprise;
- Features of taxation on Family Enterprise;
- Limitation of extraordinary checks on the activities of the family enterprise;
- Ensuring the use of public infrastructure facilities of the family enterprise
- Providing banking services to the family enterprise and lending it.

The adoption of the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “ on family entrepreneurship” ensures the further development of family business in Uzbekistan, which contributes to the increase of economic potential and employment of families as an hereditary form of private entrepreneurship.

"Family business" refers to private entrepreneurship with the use of the labor of family members without attracting hired workers. They recognize” family business " as a hereditary business that goes from generation to generation in the West. His main motivation is the organization of his family business to ensure the financial well-being of the future generation. In families in Uzbekistan, it is often common to worry about the future of children and grandchildren. But these say- actions have the property of accumulating. That is, in our time of perfection, we strive to make our children family and housing, educated, professional, business – minded and busy, but we strive to leave them more ready – made things. In our fate, when entrepreneurship on the basis of the profession of the future generation has left our business in the conditions of a market economy, we would have brought them more economic benefits. To achieve this goal, “Family entrepreneurship” is of particular importance, since it has the following advantages;

1. Thanks to the common work, all family members are united, while such cooperation leads to a greater family cohesion and strengthening;
2. Seeking to increase profits and increase family budget

3. From the youth there is an icon of attracting children to labor, then to business. Knowledge and skills in doing business from parents. Learning from adults in many cases is preferable to dry theoretical lessons, which you can take from specialists.

4. Ensure their stable and prosperous future by inheriting family work to children;

5. Employment of family members prefer to stay in their home without going far in search of a job;

6. The formation of such qualities of family members as labor, saving, initiative, entrepreneurship, responsiveness that have a socio – economic significance.

In exchange for the development of family business, household incomes will increase, and it will also be possible to create additional jobs by attracting hired workers to perform some household duties, such as cooking, gardening, childcare, driving, security.

In addition to the convenience and achievements of the “family enterprise”, it also has its drawbacks, these are the following;

- Incompetence of some family members creates problems with creating a business.
- The absence of a proven reputation in the eyes of relatives, that is, not being recognized because of insecurity, can psychologically interfere with or hinder the conduct of family business;
- Distinguish between personal and business relationships, otherwise, all family life interferes with business and may cause misunderstandings, obstacles in the course of activities;
- The occurrence of excessive laziness and arrogance in many family members can cause obstacles.

Family business has become a highly influential type of business on an international scale with its efficiency. On its basis, internationally respected

corporations have grown, which will be an example of Ford's automotive corporation. Henry Ford in his book "My Life, My achievements" states that he made an icon about the history, traditions and experiences of the emergence of family business and paid attention to the following principles in the organization of the family car business;

1. Do not be afraid of the future and learn from the past, who is afraid of the future, he loses the scope of his activities. The past is useful because it shows us the ways and means of development.
2. Do not pay any attention to the competition, let those who are good at work continue
3. Put the work on the general interest above personal gain, earnings should be decided not on the basis of profitable work, but at its end.
4. Production-does not mean a cheap purchase and a sale of value, it is the purchase of raw materials and materials with more moderate prices to turn them into a quality product that will deliver to consumers with as little additional costs as possible

Since ancient times, entrepreneurship has been an important factor for people to build their lives, lead an independent lifestyle, work with initiative and contribute to the well-being of their family and native. It remains to say that business is absorbed into the blood of our people. It should be noted that the involvement of households in family entrepreneurship contributes to the strengthening of families and expands opportunities for rational solutions to various problems arising in marriage. The conflicts associated with living in the family of entrepreneurs are significantly less than in other families. It should be noted that more than half of the entrepreneurs admit that it helps to deal with the same business to solve family problems. In the family business, as a rule, there is a distribution of drinks of functions, in which both the man and the woman, and the children who have reached puberty, are used to the labor. Consequently, the success of the family business is in an organized way, that is, in helping each of

them, in protecting corporate interests together and in keeping with family.

In conclusion, so that the “family business” in the form of hereditary entrepreneurship is not a simple business, but rather an entrepreneurial activity to deal with it, because of the characteristics of the type, each family can achieve success only when it takes initiative, organization, innovation, market Science, entrepreneurial abilities such as risk. When the Republic of Uzbekistan implements the proposals related to the development and adoption of the new law “on family business”, the family business in Uzbekistan is more developed. Parents, having started a family business in adulthood and leaving an inheritance to their children and grandchildren, seek financial security for their stable and prosperous future, as well as their old age.

REFERENCES:

1. Shadieva, G. M., & o‘g‘li Isoqulov, Z. S. (2022). WAYS TO REDUCE POVERTY. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(12), 957-962.
2. Mardievna, S. G., & Oblokulovich, K. S. (2021). Methodology for determining the role of family business in the economy. *European Business and Management*, 7(6), 199.
3. Shadieva, G. M., & Akbarovna, K. S. (2023). PROVIDING EMPLOYMENT BY IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF FAMILY BUSINESSES. *Journal of new century innovations*, 20(3), 25-31.
4. Shadieva, G., Azamatovna, T. D., & Abdukhalilovich, S. B. (2022). The role of retail trade in increasing the standard of living of the population. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429*, 11, 64-67.

5. Shadiyeva, G. (2022). The Role of Family Business in the Development of the Service Industry. *American Journal of Economics and Business Management*, 5(9), 213-218.
6. Shadiyeva, G. (2022). The Role of Family Business in the Development of the Service Industry. *American Journal of Economics and Business Management*, 5(9), 213-218.
7. Shadieva, G. M., & Akbarovna, K. S. (2023). THE CONCEPT OF "FAMILY ECONOMY", ITS DEVELOPMENT. *Journal of new century innovations*, 20(3), 32-41.
8. Shadiyeva, G. M., & Urozaliev, E. (2022). HISTORY OF RAILWAY TRANSPORT DEVELOPMENT IN OUR COUNTRY AND FOREIGN EXPERIENCES. *Eurasian Journal of Academic Research*, 2(8), 221-226.
9. Mardiyevna, S. G., & Abdusamatovich, J. J. (2022). SANOAT 4.0 KONSEPSIYASI VA UNGA TA'SIR ETUVCHI RISKLAR. *Current Issues of Bio Economics and Digitalization in the Sustainable Development of Regions*, 712-721.
10. Шакирова, Ф. Б. (2022). ИННОВАЦИОН РИВОЖЛАНИШНИ ТАЪМИНЛАШДА ХОРИЖИЙ ДАВЛАТЛАР ТАЖРИБАСИ. *Journal of new century innovations*, 17(1), 106-113.
11. Шакирова, Ф. Б. (2022). ИННОВАЦИОН РИВОЖЛАНИШ МОДЕЛЛАРИ ВА УЛАРНИНГ ИҚТИСОДИЙ ЎСИШ БИЛАН АЛОҚАДОРЛИГИ. *Journal of new century innovations*, 17(1), 101-105.
12. Шакирова, Ф. Б. (2022). ТРАНСПОРТ СОҲАСИДА ДАВЛАТ-ХУСУСИЙ ШЕРИКЛИК МЕХАНИЗМЛАРИДАН ФОЙДАЛАНИШНИНГ ХОРИЖИ ТАЖРИБАСИ. *Journal of new century innovations*, 15(3), 66-74.
13. Shakirova, F. B. (2022). INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT MODELS AND THEIR RELATIONSHIP WITH ECONOMIC GROWTH. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(10), 662-665.

14. Shakirova, F. B. (2022). ТЕМИР ЙЎЛ ТРАНСПОРТИ СОҲАСИДАГИ ДАВЛАТ-ХУСУСИЙ ШЕРИКЧИЛИК МУНОСАБАТЛАРИ. *Journal of new century innovations*, 16(3), 82-85.
15. Shakirova, F. B., & Sattorova, S. B. (2022). “О ‘ЗБЕКИСТОН ТЕМИР YO ‘ЛЛАРИ” АЖ FAOLIYATINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA XALQARO NAMKORLIK FAOLIYATI. *Eurasian Journal of Academic Research*, 2(9), 4-9.
16. Shakirova, F. B. (2022). ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА ИННОВАЦИОН РИВОЖЛАНИШНИНГ НАЗАРИЯЛАРИ, ШАКЛЛАНИШИ ВА МИЛЛИЙ ИҚТИСОДИЁТ ЎСИШИНИ ТАЪМИНЛАШДАГИ ИМКОНИЯТЛАРИ. *Journal of new century innovations*, 16(3), 86-96.
17. Шакирова, Ф. Б. (2022). ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РОСТА НА ОСНОВЕ ИННОВАЦИОННОГО РАЗВИТИЯ. *Scientific Impulse*, 1(2), 382-390.
18. Shadieva, G., & Shakirova, F. (2020). MILLIY INNOVATSION TIZIMNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA INVESTITSIYA VA INNOVATSIYALARNING O ‘RNI. *SCIENCE AND INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT*, (4), 9-16.